

BEAGLE
BLUE OCEANS STRATEGY
FOR VALUE CREATION

D2.5. Open Call

October 2024

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Work Package	2
Delivery Date	October 31 st 2024
Actual Delivery Date	October 31 st 2024
Abstract	The deliverable D2.5 Open Call is being submitted as specified in the BEAGLE Grant Agreement. The dissemination level of this deliverable is public. This deliverable demonstrates the creation of the Open Call, highlighting the value proposition and the creation of the Open Call process.

Document Revision History

Date	Version	Author/Contributor/Reviewer	Summary of Main Changes
27/09/2024	V0.1	Daniela Fonseca (F6S)	1st draft
11/10/2024	V0.2	Xiaoni Li, Yin Shi (URV)	1st revision
16/10/2024	V0.3	Maher Asal (HV), Raúl Escobar (CTAG)	2nd revision
18/10/2024	V0.4	Daniela Fonseca (F6S)	Reviewed version
21/10/2024	V0.5	Blandine Flichy (NextMove)	Review
24/10/2024	V0.6	Julia Kosikowska (UNIMOS)	Review
24/10/2024	V0.7	Ivan Souček, Ivo Stanček (SCHP)	Review
25/10/2024	V0.8	Milena Krasteva (CTBG)	Review
29/10/2024	V0.9	Pablo Sotero Sesto (CTAG), Ivana Ilic (F6S)	Review
31/10/2024	V1.0	Daniela Fonseca (F6S), Xiaoni Li (URV)	Final version

Dissemination Level and Nature of the Deliverable

PU	Public	PU
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Grant Agreement: 101131728
Programme: Horizon Europe Framework Programme (HORIZON)
Call: HORIZON-WIDERA-2023-ERA-01
Start Date of Project: January 1st 2024
Duration: 36 months

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1 Executive summary

This deliverable outlines the objectives and strategies for the Task 2.5: Open Call (OC) for recruitment of professionals. The aim of this document is to present the OC, its objectives, general guidelines, key messages and programme value proposition. As stated in the Grant Agreement “(...) D2.5 will have a 1st release for the OC for inventory of value proposition (linkage with Task 3.1)(...). The preparation includes the setup of all required Open call documents: OC text, guidelines, materials, contract templates, proposal templates, communication key messages and programme value proposition via www.f6s.com.”

The establishment of the BEAGLE OC represents a significant milestone in advancing the recruitment and collaboration of participants from the industry and academia to start mapping the innovations and new markets. The preparation of the OC includes the results of brainstorming sessions with all the partners and will deliver the ambition and specific objectives of the OC. The general requirements and recommendations are defined, as well as the criteria and the overall application process. The evaluation process and the contracting steps will be defined as well. For each one of the OCs, the information will be displayed on the website for easy access and the registration and application form available on the F6S platform.

2 Introduction

This deliverable presents the objectives, strategies, and implementation processes for Task 2.5: Open Call (OC) for the recruitment of professionals within the framework of the BEAGLE project. The OC is a strategic initiative designed to foster collaboration between key stakeholders from industry and academia. Its primary aim is to engage professionals in developing cutting-edge innovations and mapping out new market opportunities, contributing to the overall success and impact of the BEAGLE project. The OC represents a critical milestone in facilitating the exchange of knowledge, expertise, and resources across sectors, thereby accelerating the commercialization of innovative solutions.

Moreover, this deliverable provides an overview of the general requirements and recommendations for participation, ensuring that all potential applicants are well-informed about the process. The evaluation framework is designed to ensure transparency and fairness, with clear criteria for assessing proposals and selecting participants. Ultimately, the launch of the BEAGLE OC signals a major advancement in the project's efforts to build a strong network of participants and leverage their expertise to achieve the project's broader goals of innovation and market development.

This document provides comprehensive guidance on the OC's structure and processes. The OC material, such as the OC text, general guidelines, and templates, are provided below. A strong emphasis is placed on communicating the value proposition of the programme, ensuring that potential applicants clearly understand the benefits of participation. To each one of the OCs, all information and materials will be made available via the project website, with applications and registrations hosted on the F6S platform for a streamlined and user-friendly process.

This report describes the process and guidelines for the OCs. In particular, Section 3 highlights the OCs text and objectives, with an overview of the process and timeline. In Section 4, the document highlights the eligibility criteria and in Section 5, the data protection measures. Section 6 describes the application process, whereas Section 7 focuses on the evaluation, with a description of the evaluation steps and ranking. In Section 8, a template for a Collaboration Agreement is provided, together with instructions for preparation and signature. The activities during the programme are specified in Section 9, and the resources and support provided will be described in Section 10. Section 11 focuses on the responsibilities of the applicants, and the final section (12) concludes the deliverables with an overview of the report and future work.

3 BEAGLE OCs: overview

The BEAGLE project aims to recruit and foster dynamic collaborations between industry and academia, to transform research into impactful solutions, and to facilitate the emergence of sustainable value chains. The OCs will serve as catalysts for collaboration and will lead to the discovery of 20 new market niches.

BEAGLE will run two OCs to recruit: industry makers in the OC#1 and academic innovators and technology experts in the OC#2. The co-creation experiment involves collaboration between facilitators (Mixed Teams (MTs)) and the participants (industry makers, academic innovators and technology experts) working together in various emerging market niches. The MTs, acting as facilitators, are composed of representatives from academic institutions such as URV, WBU, HV, the intermediary tech-focused partner CTAG, and cluster partners including CTBG, NEXTMOVE, SCHP, and UNIMOS. Each MT is assigned specific themes that align with the competencies and expertise of these partners. The role of the MTs as facilitators is to guide and manage the recruitment process initiated through an OC within their organisations. They engage professionals, including researchers and innovators from academia and industry, within their networks to participate in the co-creation of innovative solutions.

A total of twelve permanent MTs have been established and will remain active throughout the entire innovation funnel of the BEAGLE project. These twelve MTs correspond to the twelve market niches identified by the consortium in earlier stages of the methodology, and described below.

3.1 OC objectives and topics

The OC aims to drive business growth and open new markets by leveraging industry leadership and academic expertise through 4 objectives (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Main objectives of BEAGLE OCs.

BEAGLE pioneers a unique experiment in co-creation, bringing academia and industry together to unlock new value through innovation. With a focus on the Blue Ocean Strategy, BEAGLE’s OC’s aims to discover 12 untapped market niches and co-create 20 innovation proposals with clear roadmaps for growth. Collaborating across industry clusters, universities and technology centres, BEAGLE’s 12 MTs will explore new opportunities, foster sustainable value chains, and attract investment. This initiative serves as a

catalyst for knowledge valorisation, promoting impactful change in European markets. By 2026, BEAGLE will be working on 20 action plans.

For OC#1, the aim is to recruit 120 industry makers that will provide demands of the industry, creating 60 video factsheets to be converted into 40 connections. Applicants are going to apply to 12 market niches. The purpose is to display the video factsheets from the industry and recruit 120 innovators from academia in the OC#2, to provide solutions to the industry side. For the purpose of the OCs, video factsheets are short videos that present the most relevant information about an idea or particular subject, in an engaging and visually appealing way.

The 12 niches or topics are the following (Figure 2):

1. Renewable Energy with AI
 - a. AI-driven platforms for optimising energy production, storage and distribution
2. AI-enhanced Cybersecurity
 - a. AI-driven cybersecurity solutions for real-time threat detection, anomaly detection and automated response
3. Personalised health
 - a. Personalised health services (e.g. mRNA vaccines, nutrition)
4. AI-powered Credit Risk Assessment
 - a. Generate specific and innovative product demand within the financial Service Industry
5. Drone Delivery Services
6. AI-powered Energy Consumption Analysis
 - a. AI for decarbonisation and analysis of energy consumption
7. Sustainable Mobility Hubs
 - a. Integrated sustainable transport solutions (Mobility hubs)
8. Decentralised Renewable Energy
9. Farm-to-fork Supply Chains (F2F)
 - a. Building and improving supply chains that link farmers directly with consumers through local distribution networks, digital sales platforms, and systems that reduce food waste and transportation emissions
10. Conversion of Waste CO₂
 - a. Conversion of waste CO₂ with H₂/ H₂O into hydrocarbons (synthetic fuels and/or other chemicals)
11. AI & IoT for Smart Cities
 - a. Digital, deep-tech and novel solutions (IA and IoT) for smart and sustainable cities
12. Circular Agriculture and Packaging
 - a. Transforming agri-food residues and packaging into higher-value sustainable products

Figure 2: BEAGLE 12 market niches.

3.2 OC process

The OC process can be divided into three phases: Phase I - Preparation, Phase II - Workshop execution and Phase III - Post-workshop support (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Three-phase process of BEAGLE OC.

In Phase I - Preparation, we begin by setting up the MTs, bringing together delegates from our key partners. Each team member is assigned a thematic area based on their strengths and expertise, ensuring that everyone's skills are put to the best use. At the same time, all industry and academic partners will fill in a pre-screening list targeting potential industry makers and academy innovators for the OC. Following this, F6S launches the OC, announcing it on the F6S platform, targeting industry makers in OC#1 and academic innovators in OC#2. Communication and dissemination will be performed by email to the abovementioned lists, as well as in social media, to reach wider audiences. We define clear criteria for participation and establish the evaluation process to ensure fairness and transparency. The registration phase will open, followed by a webinar. The webinar will be a 1-hour online session to present everything the participants need to know about the application process and to directly ask their questions. The structure of the webinar will be as follows: a) 5-min welcome by the OC manager (F6S), b) 10-min presentation of BEAGLE project by the consortium leader (URV), c) 30-min Presentation of BEAGLE OC by the OC manager (F6S), focusing on a brief overview of the OC, objectives, process and how to register in the F6S platform and d) 15-min Q&A where attendees are invited to ask questions about the OC (F6S, URV and CTAG). The webinar will be recorded and made available to everyone, online. For OC#1, the webinar will be held in December and for OC#2, it is expected to run in May. Recruitment will follow, in collaboration with Work Package Leaders 3 and 4, to select the top 120 applicants.

Phase II concerns Workshop Execution, where the focus shifts to meticulous planning. This includes coordinating schedules and logistics and setting up virtual rooms with all necessary resources. In the months leading up to the first workshop, from Months 9 to 14, preparations will involve finalising the workshop details and preparing training materials. Once everything is in place, we proceed with running the workshop activities, beginning with an assessment of innovation expectations. Training sessions and co-creation exercises will then be led to foster collaborative innovation, followed by the validation of the

participants' innovation demands. Upon completion, participants will receive certification, marking their successful involvement in the workshop.

The workshops will be organised by the partner CTBG, will run online, spanning three optional dates, and are set to take place after the webinar. Over the course of these three optional dates, participants will explore and identify new industry value-creation opportunities using innovative methodologies. These online sessions are designed not only to uncover potential opportunities but also to prepare participants for the subsequent phase, which involves creating video content to showcase these ideas. The workshop for the OC#1 is scheduled for the month 15th of the project, around late March 2025 and the workshop for OC#2 is scheduled for September 2025.

For OC#1, the Workshop planning for three optional dates is provided (participants may choose any one day to attend):

Step 1: Setting the Foundation – Blue Ocean Strategy and Innovation Canvas

This session will lay the groundwork with an introduction to the workshops and their goals, followed by a deep dive into the Blue Ocean Strategy, which encourages thinking beyond conventional market boundaries. This will be followed by a session on system innovation, where participants will be trained in spotting business and market innovation opportunities and how to apply these strategies to specific industry sectors. The session will conclude with the creation of the System Innovation Canvas, a tool to organise and map the insights gathered.

Step 2: Collaborating and Validating Ideas

During this session, participants will break into smaller groups and collaborate on identifying new business opportunities using the System Innovation Canvas. This collaborative co-creation session will be followed by a peer review, where the groups will share and refine their ideas, ensuring they are practical and aligned with industry needs. The validated opportunities will then be recorded in the project database.

Step 3: Finalising Ideas and Planning for the Next Steps

The final session will be dedicated to polishing and documenting the ideas developed, ensuring they are ready for submission to the project's opportunity database. The last part of the workshop will focus on preparing for the next phase, which involves creating compelling video factsheets to highlight the identified opportunities.

After the workshop completion, participants will be awarded with certificates. Afterwards, the focus will shift to Phase III, supporting teams as they create their video factsheets, ensuring the quality of these outputs and a smooth transition to the next task.

Finally, in Phase III - Post-Workshop Support, 60 selected participants will be informed and instructed to create their video factsheets, which will be registered on the F6S platform. Throughout this phase, continuous support and mentorship will be provided to ensure the quality of the video factsheets. Submission deadlines will be set, with industry submissions due by July 2025 and academic submissions by December 2025. During this phase, the innovation funnel will be managed by engaging with 120 demands from both industry and academia. From the 60 video factsheets created, BEAGLE aims to form 40 meaningful connections, leading to the development of 20 action plans that will promote and invest in innovative solutions.

3.3 Timeline

The BEAGLE project will open two OCs as a dynamic approach to value creation. These OCs invite participation from diverse disciplines, sectors, and geographic areas, aiming to create an inclusive A-I BEAGLE community. The OCs structure is planned to run in the following order. The timeline for the OC#1 is provided as an example:

1. Registration: in each OC, industry and academia participants will register through the F6S platform; the registration will be open for 3 months, for OC#1 starting on the 29th of November and up to the 28th of February.

2. Webinar OC: a webinar will be held in December (tentative date 5th of December) to share the purpose of the OC, as well as the process. This will be recorded to allow other participants to watch later.
3. Notification of acceptance: in mid-March, 120 participants will be invited to participate in the workshop.
4. Workshop: an industrial workshop will run online, to certify 120 participants as makers in April.
5. Notification as industrial makers: in May, 60 participants will be selected and notified to prepare the video-factsheets.
6. Preparation of video-factsheets: for two months, from May until June, the 60 participants will receive support from 12 MTs to prepare the video-factsheets.
7. Video-factsheets publication: the last phase of the OC and co-creation for the industry will end with the publication of the video-factsheets in July.

Through the OCs, BEAGLE is requesting the participants the innovation demand and the solutions, respectively, which will be created in the form of a video-factsheet. The applicants will be the makers of the experiment, and each applicant will present at least one innovation demand/solution, which will then be addressed to at least one of the 12 new market niches (or challenges). The participation is not limited, as one maker can apply for several niches and prepare a video-factsheet per each innovation. However, the proposals from different companies will be prioritised.

The BEAGLE OC's follow a structured timeline designed to foster innovation and collaboration at every stage. This timeline serves as a roadmap for participants to navigate the process, facilitating impactful outcomes and sustainable growth (Figure 4).

Figure 4: Timeline for BEAGLE OC#1 and OC2.

4 Selection criteria

All applicants will have to abide by the following criteria to be considered eligible for the OC's:

- Registration and submission of the video factsheets are made only through the F6S platform. Proposals submitted by any other means will not be considered.
- Only complete registrations and video factsheet submissions will be accepted. The video fact sheet should include the requested administrative data and any supporting documents specified in the OC.

- The video factsheets should have a clear dimension as part of the 12 market niches identified.
- A registration and video factsheet are only considered eligible if its contents correspond to the BEAGLE requirements, including the specific eligibility conditions set out as part of the OC guidelines.
- Registrations and video factsheets that do not comply with those criteria will be excluded and marked as ineligible.
- The registration and submission of the video factsheets are provided only in the English language.
- Registrations and video factsheets need to be submitted before the deadline.

BEAGLE will publish the call widely between the industry clusters and the academia members. It will be published on BEAGLE's website, and it will remain open for at least 2 months. If the submission deadline changes, applicants will be informed by BEAGLE. BEAGLE will publish the outcomes of the calls without delay, including a description of the video factsheets, keywords, market niche and country.

4.1 Type of beneficiary

The BEAGLE project is designed to benefit industry makers, and academic innovators. The industry makers are all the individuals/organisations that are doing business and competing in the process. The academic innovators are all the individuals/organisations that collaborate in higher education and research institutions to mobilise knowledge and innovations. The participants can apply to several niches and conduct a video factsheet per each innovation. However, proposals from different industries and academia will be prioritised.

As part of the co-creation experiment, the target beneficiaries are individual makers from partners from the BEAGLE network, i.e. partners and associates from the ecosystem of the project partners. BEAGLE will benefit beneficiaries that are represented by the partners of the project consortium. If the project is unable to secure 120 participants in each call, the consortium may need to consider extending the participation to external members. This approach will help broaden the BEAGLE outreach, ensuring sufficient engagement and the achievement of target numbers while also potentially enriching the project with diverse insights and contributions from a wider pool of stakeholders.

4.2 Target countries

Applicants must be based in any of the following countries:

- The Member States (MS) of the European Union (EU), including their outermost regions.
- The Overseas Countries and Territories linked to the Member States¹.
- Horizon Europe associated countries (Association to Horizon Europe is governed by the Horizon Europe Regulation 2021/695): according to the updated list published by the European Commission².
- The UK and Switzerland applicants are not eligible.

The ambition of the OCs is to facilitate the engagement of professionals to be part of the co-creation experiment acting as makers and innovators. To ensure the support and guidance during the co-creation stages, priority will be given to stakeholders from respective ecosystems and members of each project partner, based in Spain, France, Sweden, Poland, Czech Republic and Bulgaria.

¹Entities from Overseas Countries and Territories (OCT) are eligible for participation under the same conditions as entities from the Member States to which the OCT in question is linked.

²https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/common/guidance/list-3rd-country-participation_horizon-euratom_en.pdf

4.3 Deadline

Registration for the OCs will be open for at least two months, between the 29th of November of 2024 and the 28th of February of 2025 for OC#1 and between the 1st of May of 2025 and the 1st of July of 2025. Only registrations submitted before the deadline will be considered (closes always at 5 pm Brussels time). After the registration closure, no additions or changes will be considered. The deadline hour of submission is not flexible.

4.4 Language

English is the only official language of the BEAGLE project. Submissions done in any other language will not be eligible and will not be evaluated. English is also the only official language during the whole execution of the BEAGLE programme. This means that all communication will be in English, and all deliverables will only be accepted if in English.

5 Data Protection

To process and evaluate applications, BEAGLE will need to collect Personal Data. F6S Network Limited, as the OC coordinator will act as data controller for data submitted through the F6S platform for these purposes. The F6S platform's system design and operational procedures ensure that data is managed in compliance with The General Data Protection Regulation (EU) 2016/679 (GDPR). Each applicant will accept the F6S terms to ensure coverage. Please refer to <https://www.f6s.com/terms> to check F6S platform data privacy policy and security measures.

6 OC registration and submission process

Registration for the OC and submission of video factsheets are submitted in two stages, and the mentorship and support will be in one step, as presented in the Figure 5 below.

Figure 5: BEAGLE OCs registration and submission process.

6.1 OC publication and documentation

The OCs will be supported by the following documentation, which will be found at <https://projectbeagle.eu/open-call/>. Applicants are encouraged to consult all relevant files before proceeding with the submission.

The templates for the Open Call documents will be available on the website, and these will include: i) Guidelines for applicants (document prepared based on the information of this document) and ii) Video-fact sheet template (a document that indicates all the information that should be provided in the video factsheets that will be uploaded as part of the application form on the F6S platform).

6.2 Registration

The submission will be done through the F6S platform. For OC#1 the page was already set up and applicants will register through <https://www.f6s.com/beagle-open-call-1-industry-registration>. The applicants are required to register a profile at F6S to have access to the webinar and the workshop, and to receive support in the preparation of the video factsheets.

1. Applicants/makers are required to apply online and answer all questions at <https://www.f6s.com/beagle-open-call-1-industry-registration>
2. The information to be submitted upon registration is: Name, E-mail, Job title, Organisation, Country and indicate to which thematic niches. Tick boxes for the applicants to confirm that they accept the terms and conditions of BEAGLE OC. A general overview of the application form is in Annex 1.
3. The registration deadline will not be extended unless a major problem with the F6S platform makes the system unavailable. In case an extension is provided, all applicants will be notified.

6.3 Video factsheet submission

The video factsheets submission will be done through the F6S platform. For OC#1 the page was already set up and applicants will submit them through <https://www.f6s.com/beagle-oc1-industry-innovation>. The applicants who already registered a profile at F6S before the registration should use the same account.

1. Applicants/makers are required to submit the video factsheets online and answer all questions at <https://www.f6s.com/beagle-oc1-industry-innovation>
2. The information to be submitted during this phase is: Name, E-mail, Job title, Organisation and Country, to briefly describe the industry demand and to which of the 12 market niches it fits. Upload the link to the video factsheet. Tick boxes for the applicants to confirm that they accept the terms and conditions of BEAGLE OC.
3. The submission deadline will not be extended unless a major problem with the F6S platform makes the system unavailable. In case an extension is provided, all applicants will be notified.
4. After submission, editing is not possible. If the applicant discovers an error in the proposal and provided the call deadline has not passed, the applicant may request the Open Call BEAGLE team to re-submit the proposal. However, BEAGLE does not guarantee that a resubmission is feasible in case the request for resubmission is not received.

7 Evaluation process

7.1 Eligibility check

Eligibility to participate in the BEAGLE co-creation experiment is initially verified against several criteria. This process is carried out by the BEAGLE team. Upon registration, participants may be declared inadmissible to participate in the co-creation process. The check will verify:

1. Registration via F6S platform and defined deadline.
2. Participation of individuals from eligible countries.

A video factsheet may be declared ineligible or inadmissible at any stage. The check will verify:

1. Proposals reception: via F6S platform and by the defined deadline.
2. The video is in English.
3. The video factsheet is submitted prior to the deadline.

At this stage, eligibility criteria are checked, and if a candidate does not meet all these criteria, they will be excluded and will move to the next stage "In/Out Scope screening". The non-eligible applicants will be informed by email. No additional feedback will be given.

7.2 Evaluation/ranking

The members of the MTs will act as evaluators of the co-creation process. With the aim to guarantee and maximise the results of the co-creation experiments, the MTs will evaluate proposals from makers to ensure the generation of desired connections between Academia and Industry according to the Innovation funnel of BEAGLE.

Each MT will oversee and evaluate the proposals addressed to their specific market niche. Therefore, the proposals from makers will be scored based on the criteria in the table below (Table 1).

Table 1: Criteria employed in the evaluation and ranking of video factsheets.

Criterion	Meaning
Innovation (Weighting: 50%)	-Alignment with the BEAGLE project (experiment to co-create Academia and Industry). -Alignment with at least one of the 12 specific market niches. -Fitting with BOS (principles and characteristics).
Feasibility (Weighting: 25%)	-Opportunity to generate connections with the research community. -Business Readiness Level (BRL) up to 3. -Technological Readiness Level (TRL) up to 3.
Capacity (Weighting: 25%)	-Gender and diversity balance. -Quality and clearance of the innovation demand or offer presented by the maker.

For each criterion under examination, score values represent the justification detailed in the table below (Table 2).

Table 2: Score values and justification for evaluation.

Score	Justification
1-Poor	The proposal addresses the criterion in an inadequate manner or there are significant weaknesses.
2-Fair	The proposal addresses the criterion broadly, but there are still several weaknesses.
3-Good	The proposal addresses the criterion well, but improvements are necessary
4-Very good	The proposal addresses the criterion very well, but some improvements are still possible.
5-Excellent	The proposal successfully addresses all relevant aspects of the criterion. Any shortcomings are minor.

Each criterion will be scored between 1 and 5. Half point scores are not given. The final score (including for each criterion) is calculated based on the average of the scores. Therefore, final scores may be a decimal. The threshold for each criterion is three (3), therefore any criterion with a score less than three will disqualify the proposal. Each member of the corresponding MT will record their individual assessment of each proposal using an Individual Evaluation Report (ISR). A single Evaluation Summary Report (ESR) will be prepared, representing opinions and scores from ISR. Therefore, MTs will conduct several interactions and meetings, if required, to guarantee the collection of individual scores as well as to get a consensus for the ESR.

8 BEAGLE collaboration agreement

After the workshop delivery in Phase II, 60 participants (from industry and academia in OC#1 and OC#2, respectively) will be selected. The BEAGLE consortium will start the commitment agreement in collaboration with the representatives of the 12 MTs and the makers.

The commitment agreement will also include a declaration of honour on exclusion criteria and absence of conflict of interest. The Commitment Agreement as provided in Annex 2 is final and may not be changed, including the addition or removal of any articles or other content.

All documentation that requires a signature must be signed by hand (e.g., with the same signature on the identity card) or with a valid electronic digital signature. BEAGLE reserves the right to request one or the other types of signatures for specific documentation.

9 Resources and support during the programme

During the BEAGLE OC programme, the participants will receive the following support:

- The BEAGLE Consortium partners will provide support, guiding the applicants throughout the process.
- The 12 MTs will support participants in the development of their ideas and the creation of video factsheets.
- Invitation to BEAGLE events, namely webinars and events, all carried out online.

No financial support will be provided for this project.

10 Responsibility of the participants

10.1 Conflict of interest

Applicants must not have any current and/or potential conflict of interest with the BEAGLE consortium, the OC selection process and during the co-creation process. Applicants must formally and immediately notify the BEAGLE coordinator of any situation constituting or likely to lead to a conflict of interests and take all the necessary steps to rectify this situation.

All cases of conflict of interest will be assessed case by case. Applicants must take all measures to prevent any situation where the impartial and objective evaluation and implementation of the project is compromised for reasons involving economic interest, political or national affinity, family or emotional ties or any other shared interest ('conflict of interests'). If a conflict of interest is discovered and confirmed at the time of the co-creation process, the video factsheet will be considered as non-eligible and will not be part of the experiment.

Makers must take all measures to prevent any situation where the impartial and objective implementation of the co-creation process is compromised for reasons involving economic interest, political or national affinity, family or emotional ties or any other shared interest ('conflict of interests'). They must formally notify the BEAGLE coordinator without delay of any situation constituting or likely to lead to a conflict of interests and immediately take all the necessary steps to rectify this situation. The BEAGLE coordinator may verify that the measures taken are appropriate and may require additional measures to be taken by a specified deadline. Moreover, if the Commitment agreement is terminated, the BEAGLE might use the ideas generated during and after the workshop to continue developing the innovation funnel.

10.2 Data protection and confidentiality

Data will not be used for any purposes not identified within the BEAGLE project. Any sensitive information (partially confidential) needs to be identified and the issue raised with the BEAGLE consortium. If needed, the confidential issues need to be explicitly stated in the BEAGLE Collaboration Agreement, nevertheless participants need to be aware that the results of the co-creation experiment will be made public.

10.3 Internal communication

The operational communication channel will be the F6S Platform. For formal communications, between the BEAGLE MTs, consortium and the makers, the communication channel is email, and messaging platforms such as the MS Teams.

11 Contact

The BEAGLE Consortium provides the following support:

- Open Call Documents: <https://projectbeagle.eu/open-call/>
- For registration on the OC: www.f6s.com/beagle-open-call-1-industry-registration
- For extraordinary communication needs, please contact the Help Desk: opencall@beagle.eu
- F6S support team (for any technical issues with the F6S platform): support@f6s.com

12 Concluding remarks

The BEAGLE project's OCs guidelines are designed to stimulate collaboration, innovation, and sustainable value creation by drawing on the principles of the Blue Ocean strategy. Through these calls, BEAGLE aims to transcend traditional market boundaries and create new opportunities by engaging a diverse range of participants from different sectors, disciplines, and geographic areas. By fostering a vibrant and inclusive A-I BEAGLE community, the project seeks to leverage the collective expertise of industry innovators, academic researchers, and technology centre experts to drive forward its mission of exploring untapped markets and co-creating viable, long-term solutions.

As the foundation of BEAGLE's innovation strategy, these OCs not only seek to uncover 20 new market niches but also to co-develop 20 innovation proposals that are actionable and investment ready. With a phased approach—ranging from the discovery of opportunities to the consolidation of innovation proposals—the process ensures a structured yet flexible pathway for participants to collaborate and generate tangible outcomes. Ultimately, these open calls represent an essential vehicle for achieving BEAGLE's goal of driving impactful change in European markets, fostering sustainable value chains, and contributing to the evolution of competitive, forward-thinking industries across the continent.

Annex 1: Application form in F6S platform

A screenshot of the application form is displayed below. The "BEAGLE_test" user is used as an example.

The screenshot shows the F6S platform interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with 'Pipeline', 'Scouting', 'Apply', 'Events', 'Jobs', and 'Deals'. A search bar and a user profile for 'Daniela' are also visible. The main content area features a dark header with the BEAGLE logo and the text 'BEAGLE - OC#1 Industry registration' and 'Blue Oceans Strategy For Value Creation'. Below this, it shows 'You connected with Ivana & Daniela' and a 'DISCUSS' button. The main content is a registration form for 'BEAGLE_test' with the following sections:

- SECTION 1: APPLICANT(S) INFORMATION**
 - Name (First and last name)
 - E-mail
 - Job title
 - Organisation
 - Country
 - Indicate the niche you are applying for:
- SECTION 2: REQUIREMENTS TO JOIN BEAGLE PROGRAMME**
 - I CONFIRM that all information provided in this registration is true and correct.
 - I ACCEPT that the information provided and submitted in this registration form can be shared by F6S with the BEAGLE consortium and external mentors for the purpose of the open call.
- SECTION 3: ADDITIONAL QUESTIONS**
 - How did you hear about the BEAGLE Open Call #1 for industry?

At the bottom of the form, there are sections for 'Recommendations' and 'Ask for new Recommendations'.

Annex 2: Open Call Collaboration Agreement

This Agreement (hereinafter referred to as the "Agreement") is entered into by and between the respective Project BEAGLE consortium partner (hereinafter referred to as the "Party BEAGLE"), and the individual or organisation from said Partner's network or ecosystem selected through Project BEAGLE's open call process (hereinafter referred to as the "Participating Party"). Each of the nine Project BEAGLE consortium partners is authorised to utilise this Agreement for participants from their respective networks or ecosystems.

1. Project

1.1 This collaboration is conducted in alignment with the principles and guidelines of Horizon Europe, the European Union's key funding programme for research and innovation.

1.2 Horizon Europe aims to:

- Strengthen the EU's scientific and technological bases and the European Research Area (ERA)
- Boost Europe's innovation capacity, competitiveness and jobs
- Deliver on citizens' priorities and sustain our socioeconomic model and values

1.3 The parties acknowledge that this collaboration falls under the Horizon Europe framework and agree to adhere to its rules and regulations.

1.4 Grant Agreement: This collaboration is subject to the Grant Agreement No. [101131728] under the Horizon Europe programme. The parties agree to comply with all terms and conditions set forth in this Grant Agreement.

1.5 The parties agree to comply with all obligations set forth in the aforementioned Grant Agreement, including but not limited to reporting requirements, ethical standards, and intellectual property rights management.

1.6 The BEAGLE project introduces a dynamic approach to value creation through its open calls, which form the cornerstone of its innovation strategy. Leveraging the principles of the Blue Ocean strategy, BEAGLE aims to unearth new market niches and foster sustainable value chains in previously untapped territories. These open calls invite participation from diverse disciplines, sectors, and geographic areas, aiming to create an inclusive A-I BEAGLE community.

1.7 The process unfolds across three phases: discovering opportunities, co-creating innovation proposals, and consolidating innovative market niches to attract investment.

2. Non-Disclosure

2.1 Party BEAGLE hereby acknowledges and agrees that any information shared by the Participating Party shall be used solely for the purposes of the project implementation. All rights, including but not limited to Intellectual Property Rights, shall remain exclusively with the Participating Party. Party BEAGLE commits not to disclose any such information to third parties not directly involved in the BEAGLE activities in which the Participating Party participates. These confidentiality obligations shall remain in force during the project implementation period and shall continue to be binding in the post-BEAGLE project period of Academic-Industry BEAGLE community.

2.2 Both parties promise not to misuse any information provided during the collaboration.

3. Resource Provision

3.1 Party BEAGLE shall provide sufficient resources to support the open call and recording of video fact sheets.

4. Termination of Collaboration

4.1 According with the innovation funnel approach, in the case of passing all the phases, the collaboration would conclude in December 2026.

4.2 Both the Participating Party and Party BEAGLE may abandon or terminate this collaboration at their discretion, based on their willingness and availability.

4.3 Should either party decide to terminate the collaboration, they shall promptly notify the other party.

5. Participant Terms

The Participating Party declares:

5.1 Is not subject to a conflict of interest.

5.2 Has not made false declarations in supplying the information required by the European Commission as a condition of participation in the BEAGLE project and support programme, or does not fail to supply this information

5.3 Is entirely voluntary. In that sense, there is not foreseen any kind of monetary contribution or honorary in form of reimbursement of their dedication or contribution.

5.4 Agrees to participate in the open call activities and related workshops. In the case of moving on to the successive phases of the innovation funnel, Participating Party will be requested to submit contributions such as video-factsheet and related assets to co-create in the definition of an innovation proposal.

5.5 Agrees that Party BEAGLE has the right to use the Participating Party's image and profile, and that of their team joining the activities, strictly for portfolio management, dissemination activities, media publications and reporting to the European Commission, as well as to inform of future events and activities, strictly related to BEAGLE project and its post-project A-I BEAGLE community activities, all within the scope of the support services.

5.6 Reserves the right to remain a member of the community beyond the end of the project, without prejudice to those provided for in sections 1 and 4.

6. Miscellaneous

6.1 Any modifications to this Agreement must be agreed upon in writing by both parties.

6.2 If any provision of this Agreement is deemed invalid or unenforceable, the remaining provisions shall remain in effect.

7. Signatures

IN WITNESS WHEREOF, the parties hereto have executed this Agreement as of the date first above written.

For Project BEAGLE Consortium Partner (Engaging Partner):

Partner Organization: _____ [Please specify]

Name and Title: _____

Signature: _____ Date: _____

For the Participating Party:

Name and Title: _____

Signature: _____ Date: _____